

ARRAY SHAPE ESTIMATION

G. S. Egeland

New London Laboratory
Naval Underwater Systems Center
New London, Connecticut 06320

Abstract

A description of a method for the determination of array shape is given in three dimensions using measurements of array heading and depth taken at known points along the array, including the mathematical basis for the method. The applicability of this procedure to the determination of array shape is based on the idealization of the array, containing heading and depth sensors, as some unknown smooth curve on which both the heading of the tangent to the curve and the depth of the curve (below some convenient datum plane such as the water surface) are each measured at preselected points fixed on the curve, each point corresponding to the location of either a heading or a depth sensor in the array.

The problem of interest is that of determining the unknown coordinates of a three-dimensional space curve, as functions of the arc length along the curve, from known (or measured) values of the heading of the tangent to the curve and the depth of the curve at selected points. Let us begin by establishing a frame of reference defined by the three mutually orthogonal unit vectors \bar{i} , \bar{j} , \bar{k} , with \bar{k} directed vertically down, and with \bar{i} , \bar{j} parallel to the horizontal surface. Let C denote the unknown curve and let P_0 be some predetermined point on C , called the reference point, from which arc length along C is to be measured.

For any other point P on C , whose arc length from P_0 is s , the depth (below the surface) of P is denoted by $d(s)$, the heading of the tangent to C at P by $\psi(s)$, and the inclination of the tangent by $\phi(s)$. Heading is defined to be a non-negative angle less than 2π and is measured in the conventional way, namely clockwise in the horizontal plane (as seen from above the plane, looking in the direction of increasing depth) from the unit vector \bar{i} to the vertical plane through the vector in question, while inclination is an angle not exceeding $\pi/2$ in magnitude and is measured in the vertical plane from its intersection with the horizontal plane to the vector in question. If $\bar{t}(s)$ denotes the unit tangent vector to C at P (taken in the direction of increasing arc length on C) then it follows from the above definitions

that

$$\bar{i} \cdot \bar{t}(s) = \cos\psi(s)\cos\phi(s),$$

$$\bar{j} \cdot \bar{t}(s) = \sin\psi(s)\cos\phi(s) \quad (1a)$$

$$\bar{k} \cdot \bar{t}(s) = \sin\phi(s) \quad (1b)$$

and therefore we can express the unit tangent vector $\bar{t}(s)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}(s) = & [\bar{i}\cos\psi(s) + \bar{j}\sin\psi(s)]\cos\phi(s) \\ & + \bar{k}\sin\phi(s) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Let $\bar{r}(s)$ denote the position vector of P relative to the reference point P_0 . Then it follows from the elementary geometry of smooth space curves that

$$\frac{d}{ds}[\bar{r}(s)] = \bar{t}(s) \quad (3)$$

Now let $x(s)$, $y(s)$, $z(s)$ denote the rectangular cartesian coordinates of P , and be measured from the reference point along the three axes as determined by the unit vectors \bar{i} , \bar{j} , \bar{k} . Then we have

$$x(s) = \bar{i} \cdot \bar{r}(s), \quad y(s) = \bar{j} \cdot \bar{r}(s),$$

$$z(s) = \bar{k} \cdot \bar{r}(s)$$

and the relative position vector $\bar{r}(s)$ of P is given by

$$\bar{r}(s) = \bar{i}x(s) + \bar{j}y(s) + \bar{k}z(s) \quad (4)$$

Since the origin of coordinates has been taken at P_0 where the arc length s vanishes then we must have $x(0) = y(0) = z(0) = 0$. Therefore, letting d_0 denote the depth (below the surface) of the reference point P_0 , it readily follows that

$$z(s) = d(s) - d_0 \quad (5)$$

where

$$d_0 = d(0) \quad (6)$$

Using eqs. (2) and (4) to express the vector equation (3) in terms of its three component equations we have

$$\frac{d}{ds} [x(s)] = \cos\psi(s)\cos\phi(s)$$

$$\frac{d}{ds} [y(s)] = \sin\psi(s)\cos\phi(s) \quad (7a)$$

$$\frac{d}{ds} [z(s)] = \sin\phi(s) \quad (7b)$$

The vertical slope $m(s)$ of the curve C at P is defined by

$$m(s) = \frac{d}{ds}[z(s)] \quad (8)$$

so that from eq. (7b) we have $m(s) = \sin\phi(s)$. Note that, for convenience of expression, we have intentionally corrupted the conventional mathematical meaning of the word "slope." If $m^*(s)$ denotes the slope in the conventional sense then $m^*(s) = \tan\phi(s) = m(s)/\sqrt{1 - m^2(s)}$. Since the inclination $\phi(s)$ never exceeds $\pi/2$ in magnitude then the inclination is uniquely determined from the slope by the inverse equation

$$\phi(s) = \sin^{-1}[m(s)] \quad (9)$$

and it immediately follows that

$$\cos\phi(s) = \sqrt{1 - m^2(s)} \quad (10)$$

Using a superposed dot to denote differentiation along C , i.e., with respect to arc length s , we can now write eqs. (7a) in terms of the heading $\psi(s)$ and the vertical slope $m(s) = \dot{z}(s)$ as

$$\dot{x}(s) = \cos\psi(s) \sqrt{1 - m^2(s)}$$

$$\dot{y}(s) = \sin\psi(s) \sqrt{1 - m^2(s)} \quad (11)$$

Finally, by integrating these two equations along the curve C from the reference point P_0 (where $x(0) = 0, y(0) = 0, s = 0$), we readily find the horizontal coordinates $x(s), y(s)$ of the point P on C relative to P_0 to be given by

$$x(s) = \int_0^s \dot{x}(\sigma) d\sigma, \quad y(s) = \int_0^s \dot{y}(\sigma) d\sigma \quad (12)$$

Thus the set of equations, consisting of eqs. (5), (6), (8), (11), and (12) provide the sought after result, namely, the means for precisely determining the coordinates of the three dimensional space curve whose depth and tangent heading are known everywhere along the curve as functions of arc length. In practice however, the precision is most often limited by the fact that the actual depth and heading functions are not known directly, but only a relatively small set of values of depth and heading measurements, at selected points on the curve C , are available. Therefore it is necessary to use some sort of curve fitting technique (e.g., fitting polynomial functions of arc length to the measured data by means of least squares) in order to obtain an estimate of the depth d and tangent heading ψ as functions of arc length along the curve. Since the form of its derivative along the curve is also known, therefore it is not necessary to resort to numerical

differentiation to determine the vertical slope at any point on the curve, as required by eq. (8). Since numerical integration is relatively simple to carry out on a computer to any desired degree of accuracy, the complete set of equations, as indicated above, including the evaluation of the integrals of eq. (12), can be directly implemented on a digital computer in the form in which they are given here.

Thus the coordinates of the three dimensional space curve can be determined from measurements of depth and tangent heading at selected points on the curve with known arc lengths, by means of the procedure proposed above. Moreover it can be done in such a way that the sources of error in the coordinates are limited only to the errors of measurement (of depths, tangent headings, and arc lengths at selected points on the curve) and the modelling error implicit in the arbitrary choice of function used to fit to the measured data. More explicitly, it has not been found necessary to resort to the use of approximations in constructing this solution of the problem.

